

five seminar sessions (every Thursday, in March 2023) for about 20 hours. The course ended with awarding of certificates.

Why this capacity-building initiative should be sustained?

There is a clear recognition among health professionals that training plays a crucial role in personal development and effective health information management. Nowadays, new advanced tools for data analysis and presentation are available. Interest in meeting training needs is evident from the high participation observed in PHIRI capacity-building activities.

The diversity of capacity-building activities developed by different partners was collected as it also represents important knowledge to respond to the different needs of national population health experts depending on their level of training and their respective national health and care systems. In order to consolidate the outlined strategy and achieve the desired results, the commitment of all stakeholders is required. It is through the collaborative organization of capacity-building activities, with partnerships between European networks and projects, as well as the network of contacts built by the PHIRI Project, that the capacity to train the public health workforce for sustainability, preparedness, and the ability to innovate health systems in times of crisis can develop and evolve⁵

PROVED VALUE OF THE ESHI

- * New digital and data analytical tools for population health are emerging, which requires the development of adequate multidisciplinary training. The European context is a good lever to promote collaboration and bring in the best European experts on the HI topics and making them familiar with the [Health Information Portal](#).
- * The strategy developed emphasises collaboration, leveraging a set of European projects that have contributed to mitigate health information inequalities in Europe.
- * Cross-country exchange and mutual learning are impetus tools to leverage the HI knowledge and expertise that exists and is available to contribute to the improvement of Europe's resilience to the health crisis.

References

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- ³ Lapão L, Beja A, Tolonen H, Craig S, Eaton K, Fernandes GV, et al. Roadmap for Capacity Building Programme for EU MS. European Health Information Training Programme [Internet]. 2020; Available from: www.inf-act.eu
- ⁴ PHIRI Spring School on Health Information 2023 (<https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/activities/spring-school-health-information>)
- ⁵ Peyroteo M, Maia MR, Paulo MS, Saso M, Schutte N, Bogaert P, Habl C, Lapao, LV. (2023) Strengthening European capacity building on health information. European Journal of Public Health XXXX

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